

ANID
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Ministerio de
Ciencia, Tecnología,
Conocimiento e
Innovación

ANID Action Plan Supporting CoARA Commitments

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I. Introduction

The National Research and Development Agency (Agencia Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo – ANID) is the Chilean state agency belongs to the Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation that manages and executes programmes and instruments that promote, foster and develop research in Chile, in all areas of knowledge. It was created in 2018 as the successor of the CONICYT with a new mandate: to achieve greater participation and connection between the actors of the STI system, linking knowledge and its application for the benefit of citizen which delivered the opportunity to propose a new way of managing and using the knowledge that is produced with public funds.

This mission is carried out through its five sub-directorates:

- The Human Capital Sub-directorate seeks to contribute to the increase of advanced human capital for the development of the country's science and technology by funding postgraduate master and doctoral scholarships in Chile and abroad for graduates and professionals of academic excellence. This sub-directorate also seeks and promotes mechanisms to early engage of postgraduates with academia and the productive sector.
- The Research Projects Sub-directorate labour is to strengthen the research excellence driven by curiosity and focused on strategic areas stimulating and promoting national and global scientific and technological development through individual and group scientific research in various areas of knowledge. It allocates resources through different types of the National Fund for Scientific and Technological Development, Fondecyt, created in 1981 as the main public instrument to support research in basic science and technological development in Chile.
- The Centres and Associative Research Sub-directorate seeks to promote collaboration in research conducted in Chile by funding, coordinating and connecting a network of groups scientific research and centres of excellence in cutting-edge research and technological development with a national presence and global impact. It promotes associative research understood as research in which work teams (including researchers, knowledge management professionals, technology transfer experts and students, among others) are formed to conduct interdisciplinary research, solving complex problems in science and technology from different perspectives and aiming for broad solutions.
- The Applied Research and Innovation Sub-directorate labour is to create, disseminate and transfer scientific and technological knowledge and capabilities in close collaboration and partnership with firms and entrepreneurs, civil society, the state and academia through the management and implementation of programmes and instruments that promote the production of applied knowledge in science, technology and innovation.
- The Networks, Strategy and Knowledge Sub-directorate creates, designs and implements territorial, national and international mechanisms and strategies that streamline the integration of science, academia, the public sector and the productive sector as well as strengthen the production of scientific knowledge and democratise access to it. It collaborates and coordinates with the others sub-directorates emphasising strategic issues and links

with the science, technology, and innovation community and other sectors through the design of instruments and initiatives for joint work. Also, it manages ANID services through different platforms for access to data and scientific knowledge as components of R&D activities.

In October 2023, ANID signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment (ARRA) and joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). It was the first organisation to join CoARA in Chile. Following this milestone, ANID began a process of reflection and systematisation of research assessment experiences across the agency's various sub-directorates, with the aim of highlighting progress to date, sharing best practices and gathering evidence to further develop those processes that appear most promising. This was built on the foundation of the work that ANID had already been doing in research assessment.

This plan outlines past and current initiatives, and recommendations, to be developed over the course of two years period to advance steps to contribute the assessment of research and researchers recognising the diverse outputs and professional profiles and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research towards open science practices.

II. Past and current actions

This section reports advances in research assessment before and after ANID joined the Coalition and the information is organised according to the ten commitments that CoARA signatories must adopt.

Commitment 1: Recognise the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research

ANID incorporates the diversity of contributions in some of its instruments, for example:

- In 2023, the Research Projects Sub-directorate updated the curriculum assessment criteria which included a wider variety of products to be considered in the Regular Fondecyt instrument. Specifically, for the Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Assessment Group, it was proposed to consider the researcher's position as author in scientific articles in journals indexed in Web of Science and Scopus. In addition, the criteria were standardised for each Assessment Group to clarify the research contributions to be considered and the documents required to certify them.
- The Sub-directorate of Centres and Associative Research standardised the assessment of applications for millennium instruments (nucleus and institutes) to incorporate a greater number of contributions (from research to innovation and entrepreneurship) and make them more relevant to the project for which researchers are applying. This gives applicants the opportunity to choose and present three to five relevant contributions and limits the curriculum assessment stage making the process more efficient.

ANID incorporates the diversity of careers in some of its instruments, for example:

- Since 2019 the Fondecyt Postdoctoral and the Fondecyt Initiation instruments both from the Research Projects Sub-directorate have incorporated the academic and research career of the lead researcher as part of the curriculum assessment replacing the

productivity factor with the career factor as one of the project assessment factors.

- Starting in 2022 postgraduate scholarships administered by the Human Capital Sub-directorate incorporate the applicant's academic background and work experience into their assessment of academic career criteria. Therefore, in addition to considering teaching and research activities other activities are also considered such as participation in projects and work teams in the productive sector or in public policy programmes, scientific consulting in Ministries, among others. Likewise, to broaden the scope of contributions to be considered in the productivity of applicants, those associated with applied research, innovation, entrepreneurship, and artistic creation are now included.
- In some instruments of the Sub-directorate of Applied Research and Innovation (e.g. IDeA calls) the assessment of work teams in the proposals is prioritised over the assessment of each of the members and the contributions they can make individually.

ANID incorporates the gender perspective in its instruments, for example:

- The postgraduate scholarships administered by the Human Capital Sub-directorate incorporate a gender perspective in the assessment of applications. Currently, children during the assessment period are also a factor to consider in the criteria for career and/or academic performance in the case of female applicants, for example, in the case of scientific productivity in the context maternity leave and childcare.
- In 2020, and for the only time, the Millennium Institute Call of the Sub-

directorate of Centres and Associative Research included, as the third and fourth tiebreaker criteria, proposals whose director or alternate director was a female researcher, when the merit of the finalist proposals was equal in scoring, to reduce the gender gap. Currently, there are no gender equality requirements for submitting proposals; however, there are other criteria related to the gender distribution of the teams applying.

- To reduce the gender gap, the three modalities of the Research and Development in Action instrument (IDeA R&D, IDeA Technological Research and IDeA Advanced Technologies) of the Applied Research and Innovation Sub-directorate have implemented three measures: i) if the projects applied with a woman as the project director, changes in this position during the execution of the project cannot consider persons of male sex, ii) provide a bonus to projects that are suggested for approval and that consider a woman in the role of director and iii) consider in the project assessment process a tiebreaker criterion associated with the gender parity policy in the event that two or more proposals obtain the same assessment score, favouring the proposal with the greatest gender balance within the research team or the project whose director is a woman.
- In the Alma, Quimal and Gemini Astronomy Funds instruments of the Networks, Strategy and Knowledge Sub-directorate it are assigned extra points to proposals directed by a woman as the principal investigator, those whose sponsoring institution is located in a region other than the metropolitan region and those whose activities are carried out in region other than the metropolitan region. This action aims to reduce the gender and territorial gaps.

ANID incorporates the territorial perspective in its instruments, for example:

- The Human Capital Sub-directorate incorporates the territorial perspective in the assessment pointing out that: i) applicants can access bonds in the final score by proving acceptance into a programme (host university) in a region of Chile other than the Metropolitan, obtaining their bachelor's or professional title (university of origin) or primary or secondary education license (schooling) in a region of Chile other than the Metropolitan, ii) there is a sub-criterion of the applicant's obligations with a territorial perspective where applicants must contribute back not only to scientific and social development but also the territorial contribution, that is, the programme is carried out in universities in regions other than the metropolitan and iii) in the particular case of international scholarships to pay back them holders who have returned to Chile and reside in regions other than the Metropolitan must prove their residence time in Chile for the same duration as the scholarship. This is unlike scholarship recipients residing in the Metropolitan Region who must prove their residence time in Chile for twice the duration of the scholarship.

ANID incorporates the open science perspective in its instruments, for example:

- The Networks Strategy and Knowledge Sub-directorate bases the assessment of some of its instruments on open science (e.g., Knowledge 2030 and Engineering for 2030) thereby linking results between projects funded by the same sub-directorate and others from other sub-directorates, for example, those aimed at meeting the needs of industry and society in order to amplify the impact of the projects.

Commitment 2: Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators

In the assessment processes ANID considers the qualitative evaluation of applications and projects conducted by national and/or international peer reviewers and various relevant Committees (Committee of Programme, Assessment Committee, Committee of Area, Joint Committee, Technical Advisory Committee) for each instrument and call. These committees provide feedback and rate their reviews using a standard scoring scale (see next point). Evaluator profiles are relevant to the type of project and there are different profiles depending on the instrument, e.g. academic profiles, productive sector profiles.

ANID uses a standard scoring scale ranging from zero (failed) to five (excellent) to rate the stages and assessment criteria established in the call rules. All call rules contain a grading scale with each grade associated with its meaning and description. The scores are arranged in descending order and a ranking is compiled to accompany the recommendations for awarding proposals.

ANID bases research assessment on qualitative evaluation and peer review is central, for example:

- The assessment of applications for postgraduate scholarships administered by the Human Capital Sub-directorate uses parameterised components with scores calculated using formulas approved by institutional resolution and published in conjunction with the opening of the calls. These components respond to the annual guidelines of the Public Sector Budget Law through budget allocations for national and international scholarships. These components assess applicants'

academic background based on their grade point average for their bachelor's degree, professional degree or equivalent, and their undergraduate graduation ranking depending on their ranking in their graduating class or degree programme, for national scholarships. Additionally, for international scholarships there is a parameterised component to assess the level, quality and track record of the foreign institution and study programme. This allows applicants to know in advance of their application the scores they will receive based on the respective criteria and the methodology used to obtain those scores. The methodology was revised in 2020, and adjustments were made that remain in place today. Applicants can simulate their academic record score and their ranking score for academic and non-academic foreign institutions by OECD sub-area using the simulator software tools available on ANID's website.

- Since 2020 the Fondecyt Initiation instrument from the Research Projects Sub-directorate has incorporated a double-blind evaluation system which was a change implemented within the framework of the Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge, and Innovation's gender policy establishing two evaluation stages.
- The application and assessment process for the Global Healthy Longevity Challenge (NAM) instrument of the Applied Research and Innovation Sub-directorate is streamlined requiring the completion of a two-page application form and a short four-slide presentation. Furthermore, the evaluation is blind.

Commitment 3: Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based metrics, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index

In Chile the current legislation indicates that the accounting of scientific output from Web of Science (WoS) and Scientific Electronic Library Online (SciELO) is used to distribute monetary fiscal contributions to universities.

Also, at the national level the allocation of resources based on performance to universities is based on the accounting of publications indexed in Scopus.

On the other hand, ANID uses own rankings and publication-based metrics in research assessment, for example:

- In the Human Capital Sub-directorate, the ranking of institutions to qualify the level, quality and trajectory of the foreign institution and study programmes is of its own creation and is constructed according to the level of scientific productivity of the institutions using bibliometric data from InCites (Web of Science, Clarivate Analytics).
- For the Fondecyt Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Assessment Group of the Research Projects Sub-directorate it was proposed to consider and assign specific scores according to the researcher's position as author in the scientific article of journals indexed in Web of Science and Scopus.

Commitment 4: Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment

The Human Capital Sub-directorate develops its own rankings for i) the grade point average of applicants' bachelor's degree, professional degree or equivalent, ii) the undergraduate graduation ranking depending on the percentage where the

applicant is placed in their graduating class or degree, and iii) the level, quality and trajectory of the foreign institution and study programme. This ranking of institutions is divided into academic and non-academic institutions and is ordered according to their level of scientific productivity for each of the 39 OECD subareas based on bibliometric data from InCites (Web of Science, Clarivate Analytics). The use of these rankings is justified by: i) the operationalisation of the indications that the Public Sector Budget Law made to ANID through the specific notes in which national and international postgraduate scholarships are assigned, ii) the legitimacy by applicants of the use of parameterised components in the assessment methodology observed by the low rate of complaints associated with the assignment of scores, and iii) the efficiency in the assessment process of the applications that is exhaustive and includes several stages, in the rapid delivery of the results and in the optimisation of institutional resources. For the period 2017-2024 an average of 301 applications were received for the International Doctoral Scholarships (Becas Chile) with 2017 receiving the highest number of applications (394) and an average of 2,512 applications for National Doctoral Scholarships for the period 2017-2025 with 2025 receiving the highest number of applications (3,359). The results of the latest calls for National and International Scholarships were published two and a half months from the closing date for receiving applications.

Commitment 5: Commit resources to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes committed to

In all ANID Sub-directorates there are experienced professionals and work teams who reflect on and have implemented

changes in assessment processes/models of the instruments they administer.

More specifically:

- In the Human Capital Sub-directorate, the professionals worked with the Assessment Committees, the Technical Advisory Committee, and mathematical and statistical experts in the review and modification of the parameterised components of the application evaluation.
- In the Research Projects Sub-directorate, the professionals worked with the Assessment Groups of the different areas, the Scientific Coordination, technical analysts and project executives of the sub-directorate to study and make improvements to the assessment criteria and elaboration of the Fondecyt Project Evaluation Guide.
- The Networks, Strategy and Knowledge Sub-directorate has allocated staff hours to work on research assessment activities after ANID signed the ARRA and joined CoARA including the research and systematisation of the experiences and best practices on ANID research assessment.

Commitment 6: Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes

The formation of the Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge and Innovation and ANID as the successor to CONICYT initiated a process of reviewing and improving the research instruments with the aim of helping to ensure greater equity among those applying for scholarship programmes. This process included the study and proposed changes to the 2020 undergraduate academic record parameterisation algorithm of the Human Capital Sub-directorate.

The assessment processes for both applications and projects of the different ANID's sub-directorates consider more than one stage including quantitative and qualitative evaluation using different tools relevant to each of the instruments, e.g., assessment of individual researchers' CVs, assessment of research groups, assessment of background CVs, evaluation through interviews, own rankings, etc.

The Fondecyt Research Project Evaluation Guide from the Research Projects Sub-directorate updated in 2023 is an important tool that establishes the review and evaluation process for applications submitted to calls which guides and provides the technical guidelines for the work of evaluators and the Assessment Groups in charge of this task.

The Sub-directorate of Centres and Associative Research emphasises that for the submission and assessment of proposals for the Anillos instrument it uses the metadata from the institutional platform Researcher Portal (<https://investigadores.anid.cl/>) to record scientific productivity as a reference and guide. The ANID Researcher Portal is currently being updated to include a wide range of scientific output beyond scientific articles and books and other elements are being incorporated into the curriculum.

ANID has updated the institutional Repository (<https://repositorio.anid.cl/home>) with new collections to comply with the Open Access Policy obligations and a more user-friendly interface for diverse audiences.

ANID is evaluating to propose a National Chapter of CoARA.

Commitment 7: Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use

In July 2024, ANID co-produced the International Seminar “Fair Assessment of Science and Quality of the Higher Education System in Chile” that brought together different actors from the STI community to reflect on new models for research assessment and opened a space for a dialogue to share experiences within the framework of the transition toward open knowledge. Key notes speakers participated in the event. More information at https://accesoabierto.anid.cl/seminario_evaluacion/

In December 2024, ANID produced the event Jóvenes ConCiencia to foster collaboration and interdisciplinary work among young researchers from ANID' Centres with presentations, roundtable discussions and other activities aimed at generating reflection on the management, importance, and impact of open research data. An international expert participated in the event. More information at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Jy8ln7JL5I4>

Also in December 2024, ANID organised the conference “Open Research Data: How to Transition from Infrastructure to Services” where participants reflected on the challenges and opportunities in open research data management in Chile. An international expert participated in the event. More information at <https://accesoabierto.anid.cl/datos-de-investigacion-abiertos/>

The Research Projects Sub-directorate has developed guidelines and conducted training on the assessment processes of the instruments it administers. This includes the Fondecyt Research Project Evaluation Guide to study and test

evaluation guidelines in the Explorer instrument which has allowed for reflection and review of assessment factors and methods, evaluation guidelines for the implementation of blind evaluation for Assessment Groups, evaluation guidelines for project executives and in 2020 an international seminar reviewing international experiences with blind evaluation with Assessment Groups. More information at <https://anid.cl/seminario-anid-abre-la-discusion-sobre-modelos-de-evaluacion/>

Commitment 8: Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition

In August 2024 ANID formed a Working Group on Research Assessment with professionals of the five sub-directorates to reflect, exchange best practices and experiences on assessment models and to work in improvement the ANID assessment processes.

In January 2025 ANID formed an Expert Group on Research Assessment with research vice rectors from universities who have vast experience in the design and implementation on new forms of research assessment.

ANID professionals have participated in the General Assembly meetings and other meetings organised by CoARA.

Commitment 9: Communicate progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments

In May 2024, the Deputy Director of the Networks, Strategy and Knowledge Sub-directorate made a presentation for the Deputy Directors of the others sub-directorates and department heads where explained the meaning and commitments to be part of CoARA and proposed an action

plan. It is recognised that adherence to the principles and implementation of CoARA's commitments must be evaluated in context.

Commitment 10: Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research

In November 2024, ANID professionals from the Networks, Strategy and Knowledge Sub-directorate gathered experiences in research assessment of the different sub-directorates from primary sources through interviews with the work teams and from secondary sources such as institutional reports, guides and presentations, institutional databases and resolutions and information published on ANID's website. Then they systematised those experiences and wrote a report.

Examples of the evaluation of practices and criteria based on evidence are:

- In 2020 the Human Capital Sub-directorate reviewed the methodology for calculating undergraduate academic records to evaluate applications for postgraduate scholarships making adjustments that remain in place to this day. Members of the Mathematical Sciences Assessment Committee, members of the sub-directorate's Technical Advisory Committee, mathematical and statistical experts, the National Director of ANID and professionals from the sub-directorate participated in this process. Simulations were conducted and scenarios were built using real data from previous calls. This revision is published on the ANID website and is accessible to anyone.
- In 2021 and 2022 the Research Projects Sub-directorate reviewed and evaluated the double-blind evaluation changes incorporated into the Fondecyt Initiation

instrument adjusting the assessment stages and adding the anonymisation requirement as an admissibility criterion. An initial examination of the results of the double-blind evaluation showed that the most visible effects of its implementation are relatively recent, and it takes time to observe the changes. The double-blind evaluation was highly valued by participants in the 2023 ANID Working Groups which analysed gender, territorial and disciplinary gaps in addressing potential biases in the process. It is recognised that simultaneous changes in the assessment model (in trajectory and in double-blind evaluation) complicates the analysis as does the evaluation at different stages.

- In 2023 the Research Projects Sub-directorate made changes to the curriculum assessment criteria for Assessment Groups. The Scientific Coordination provided evidence through data analysis, scenario construction and the elaboration of graphs to present and support the proposals and including as many contributions as possible considering progressive changes, respecting the autonomy of the Groups, safeguarding the impartiality of the interests of their members and ensuring the feasibility of implementing the changes in the both platforms: ANID Curriculum Evaluation System (SEC - for its Spanish acronym) and the ANID Online Evaluation System (SEL - for its Spanish acronym).
- In 2023 the Research Projects Sub-directorate published an update to the Fondecyt Research Project Evaluation Guide which brings together all the changes introduced in recent years to Fondecyt instruments.
- The Research Projects Sub-directorate's Exploration Project Call (launched for the first time in 2022) has allowed for exploration and testing of evaluation

guidelines and reflection on assessment factors and methods.

- In the Research Projects Sub-directorate proposals for changes regarding the diversification of research products, the incorporation of diverse professional careers and double-blind evaluation, all within Fondecyt instruments were discussed and supported with analysis of data from previous years' calls. International experiences were also reviewed, and guidelines were designed and implemented. In 2020, a seminar was held with the Assessment Groups to review international experiences with blind evaluation. A variety of indicators using different sources of information and data from previous years' calls were used to assess the quality of the evaluation process and its impact on bias reduction.

III. Recommended longer-term actions

The below suggestions are based on shared experiences and comments from the sub-directorates work teams to advance reflection and changes to ANID's research evaluation models and processes.

1.- The formation of ANID in January 2020 as an Agency part of Chile's new scientific and technological institutional framework, led by the Ministry of Science, Technology, Knowledge, and Innovation and as the successor to CONICYT (National Research and Development Commission), has a vision that reinterprets and enriches the work developed by its predecessor, aligned with the country's current needs and serving the society. In this context, rethinking the Agency's role in relation to the management and use of knowledge produced with the public funds allocated also means rethinking ways of evaluating

research. It is therefore necessary to create working opportunities to reflect and rethink research evaluation models in terms of the purpose of the evaluations, projects, researchers, products to be considered, methodologies, tools, and sources of information to be used, quality metrics, scientific-technological and economic-social impact metrics, among others.

2.- The gathering of information in 2024 on research evaluation experiences presented in this document revealed a need of documentation and systematisation of the changes that the sub-directorates have discussed and implemented, as well as the decisions that justify those changes. Having a registration procedure and a digital space where the sub-directorates can document their own experiences and share information would contribute to the institutional record and memory on the institutional research evaluation.

3. - The sub-directorates work teams acknowledge the need of the Agency's own studies that include state-of-the-art information, experiences and best practices on national and international research evaluation models to propose and technically support decisions and changes in evaluation processes, as well as the decisions reported by the Ministry of Science. Furthermore, a need of evidence, studies, results, and evaluation of ANID's own practices and their impact on the ecosystem was detected. Also, technical support to advance these types of studies and analyses is required. ANID's Department of Studies and Strategic Management is crucial for implementing actions and addressing this issue.

4.- ANID opens around 80 calls per year and offers a wide variety of different types of funding from postgraduate scholarships to funding to support basic research, technological development, innovation and entrepreneurship, with multiple scopes on individual and joint projects, on

institutional strengthening. It is necessary to analyse how to articulate ANID's instruments to strengthen the STI ecosystem and more efficiently leverage its skills. To begin a diagnosis, it is possible to apply a theoretical framework to evaluate and characterise each of its instruments according to the level of sophistication in the management of the instrument, the degree to which the instrument promotes and values the production of new scientific knowledge and the degree to which it promotes and values the practical application of knowledge, and using a portfolio view that allowed the instruments to be classified. From there, a proposal was made to improve the programmatic offering and restructure the portfolio of projects to be funded. This view can offer a conceptual framework for rethinking the design and orientation of the instruments, considering the need to broaden the scope and include new research evaluation metrics that go beyond bibliometric indicators and can capture contributions to understanding multidimensional problems and the ability to guide solutions. The sub-directorates work teams recognise that the diversity of instruments complicates the methods and processes of research evaluation, however, finding common areas of evaluation among sub-directorates would allow for synergies.

5.- ANID receives a large volume of proposals (applications) and projects for evaluation, which entails significant effort and costs that impact evaluation times and budget execution deadlines. The quality of evaluations and feedback is valuable for both applicants and beneficiaries. In addition, analysts and project executives perform routine administrative tasks that often leave no time to reflect and rethink their own practices. The use of artificial intelligence in some tasks can contribute to reducing time and making processes more efficient, which would allow time to be allocated to more complex activities.

Review the Agency's procedures and differentiate team tasks, focusing them, for example, on monitoring and control teams, teams in charge of expense reports, teams in charge of research evaluation, etc. could contribute to the new challenges and new mandates of ANID and have evaluations that are more consistent with these new agency missions.

6.- To continue with the recommendations and work of the Working Group and Expert Group on Research Assessment the following topics are suggested:

- i) maintain reviewing international experiences on research evaluation relevant to the Chilean ecosystem,
- ii) agree on a proposal to integrate existing CoARA Working Groups,

iii) evaluate the formation of a working group between ANID and the Ministry of Science to jointly address topics of interest,

iv) promote the exchange of best practices and experiences based on open science projects fund by ANID and execute by universities to open science capacity building (proyectos InES Ciencia Abierta in Spanish), and

v) communicate, raise awareness, and disseminate ANID's progress on research assessment to stakeholders.

